

Observation of a male Alpine chamois (*Rupicapra rupicapra*) outside its known distribution in Liguria, north-western Italy

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Independent zoological observation

Date of document: 7 March 2026

Abstract

On 6 March 2026, a single male individual of the Alpine chamois (*Rupicapra rupicapra*) was observed in Liguria, north-western Italy, outside the currently documented distribution of the species. The animal was recorded at approximately 450 m above sea level in a rocky habitat characterized by Mediterranean vegetation dominated by *Erica arborea*. According to occurrence data available from GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility) and iNaturalist, the nearest confirmed records are located approximately 100 km from the observation site. This document provides preliminary documentation of the observation.

Observation

Date: 6 March 2026

Time: approximately 12:00 CET

Location: Liguria, Italy

Coordinates: 44.47077° N, 8.69520° E

Elevation: approximately 450 m above sea level

Habitat: rocky slope with Mediterranean vegetation. The dominant plant species in the area was *Erica arborea*.

A single individual of the Alpine chamois (*Rupicapra rupicapra*) was observed at the location described above. The animal was first detected at a distance of approximately 300 meters. The observer then approached and photographed the individual using a smartphone at an approximate distance of 30 meters.

The individual showed the characteristic morphology of the species, including the typical body shape and backward-curved horns. Shortly after the photograph was taken, the individual fled from the observation area.

Distribution context

The Alpine chamois (*Rupicapra rupicapra*) is typically associated with alpine and subalpine environments in European mountain systems. In Italy the species occurs mainly within the Alpine region.

Occurrence data available through GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility) and iNaturalist indicate that the nearest confirmed observations are located approximately 100 km from the observation site.

This observation may represent a dispersing individual occurring outside the main distribution range of the species.

Figure

Figure 1. Male Alpine chamois observed in Liguria, Italy (6 March 2026).

